

Utilization of (*Moringa Oleifera*) Leaf and Rough Lemon Peels (*Citrus Limon*) Flour Blends in Nutrient Fortification of Home Made Snacks (Cakes and Buns)

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Jacinta A. Opara**-Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences -Kampala International University Kampala, Uganda

⁽²⁾ **Ozioma C. Azubuikwe** Department Of Home Sciences/Hospitality Management and Tourism Micheal Okpara University Of Agriculture Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

Abstract:

The study was conducted on the chemical composition and organoleptic attributes of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends. 20 panelists filled the questionnaire on the sensory evaluation. The data collected was analyzed using the ANOVA of SPSS to determine the mean and the standard deviation. The study examined the chemical composition and organoleptic attributes of cakes and buns fortified with Drum stick leaf (*Moringa oleifera*) and rough lemon peels (*Citrus limon*) flour blends. Cake and buns had its macro and micro nutrients but when fortified with moringa leaf and rough lemon peels could add more value and nutrient to these products. The study was an experimental research design of one way ANOVA. The population of the study were 14 lectures and 43 final year students of Home Science department. 20 panelist form the sample size of the study, these was chosen through a random sampling techniques. 9-point hedonic likert scale questionnaire was used to determine the organoleptic attributes of the samples. This work revealed that cake and buns were produced from wheat flour and quantities of moringa leaf and rough lemon peels (1%, 2% and 3%) respectively with cake from 100% wheat flour used as control. Chemical analysis carried out on the cake sample include calcium, magnesium, sodium, iron and phosphorus. All parameters determined showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in cake and buns sample. Cake and buns with more moringa leaf and rough lemon peels had 160.50 ± 0.71 Ca, 64.35 ± 0.21 Mg, 20.05 ± 0.07 P, 82.45 ± 0.07 Na and 10.40 ± 0.14 Fe (cake). 290.00 ± 1.41 Ca, 71.00 ± 0.56 Mg, 145.90 ± 0.14 Na, 4.97 ± 0.01 Fe and 18.85 ± 0.91 P (buns). Control sample that was not fortified with moringa leaf and rough lemon peels had least mineral content. Sensory evaluation showed significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between control (100% wheat) and other samples. In taste, colour, flavor, texture and general acceptability. The cake and buns sample with 1% moringa and 1% rough lemon peels addition was the most preferred in terms of colour, taste and flavor and general acceptability. Moringa leaf and rough lemon peels could be used in fortification of bakery products

Key words; Fortification, *moringa olrifera*, utilization, Rough lemon peles

Introduction

Wheat flour has being the most commonly used for preparing snacks like cakes, buns, bread, pasta, cookies, etc. Wheat could have a negative effect for people who are sensitive to gluten (a protein found in wheat). Weight has most contain a biochemical compound called lectin. Lectin was associated with insulin resistance, higher blood pressure and higher inflammation levels. *Moringa* has two times protein found in yoghurt, rough lemon peels promotes weight loss, they contain a component know as pectin, which is responsible for the promotion of weight loss in the body. These are also helpful in decreasing the cholesterol level in the body which results in maintaining good health of our hearts. For this reason, it has put as the most nutritious vegetables plant around and has been used for fortification in cakes. This work tend to combine wheat flour, *moringa* leave and rough lemon peel in the production of cakes and buns. This will increase the nutritional status of consumers, especially children, teenagers and women that are the major consumers of snacks like cakes and buns

The consumption of cakes and other baked aerated wheat flour products has spread in Nigeria and other developing countries of the world. Wheat which is popular and unique among other aerated baked products can only grow in very few developing countries. Wheat is one of the world's most commonly consumed cereal grains. It comes from a type of grass (*Triticum*) that is grown in countless varieties world wide. The exceptions are where there is a temperate zone caused by high latitudes or high attitude or both (examples are Mexico, Northern India, Eastern Africa) (Dendy, 2001). Nigeria cannot grow wheat in large quantities. Wheat is imported from temperate countries that have surplus. Wheat is grown on more than 218,000, hectares (540,000,000 acres), (2015). A larger area than for any other crop. World trade in wheat is greater than for all other crops combined. These imports are paid for with scarce foreign currency and this, no doubt, is depleting Nigeria's external currency earnings and reserve. In the bid to lower or stop out rightly imports of wheat, the Nigeria government and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2006) have encouraged the use of composite flours and blends of wheat flours for the production of aerated products such as cakes, biscuit, buns, bread etc. It was on this note that the researcher claimed it necessary to research of fortifying cake and buns with *moringa* leaf, rough lemon peels flour to enrich the nutritive value.

Moringa Oleifera which has been described as the most nutritious vegetable plant because of its excellent and enormous benefits. It is entirely edible from leaves to roots; virtually every part of it is edible. The leaves contain significant sources of minerals and vitamins A, B and C. It contains high level of calcium, phosphorus, iron, protein with low fat and carbohydrates, (Price, 2000; Olushola, 2006). *Moringa* is a special food for the tropics, because the tree is in full leaf at the end of food scarce (Iwu, 1993). It is available all year round. Fugile, (2001) describes *moringa* as an extremely valuable food source because of its high nutrient profile. The seeds are eaten like peas or roasted like nut while the flowers are eaten when cooked and taste like mushrooms (Price, 2000; Olushola, 2006). Research had shown that ounce for ounce of *moringa* leaves contain seven times the vitamin C found in oranges, four times the vitamin A in carrots, four times the calcium found in milk, three times the potassium found in banana and two times the protein found in yoghurt. For this reason it has put *moringa* as the most nutritious vegetable plant around and has been used for fortification in cakes, noodles, bread, biscuit, buns, porridge and a hot of local, traditional or indigenous foods like garri, yam flour etc. (*Moringa* source LLC, 2012). It is also known to be the best nutritional support for nursing mothers because, it is not only rich in nutritional content but for its medicinal properties as well. As a result these nutritive values of *moringa*, it has been found to increase the volume of breast milk produced by lactating mothers. *Moringa* is also noted for its anti-bacterial action. French Scientists had found that *moringa* contains an antibacterial peptide (a molecule composed of two or more amino-acids, the building blocks of protein) that can destroy he cell membrane of many infectious bacteria (Arnold, 2007).

More so, Rough lemon peels are excellent source of fiber, potassium, magnesium, calcium, folate and beta carotene. Lemon peels improve bone health. They contain high amounts of calcium and vitamin C, lemon peels have been shown to aid preventing osteoporosis, inflammatory polyarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. Rough lemon peels can be used for fortification in cakes and buns. It can be use in reduction of oxidative stress, help fight cancer.

Snacks are important for toddlers and preschoolers because their stomach is smaller and they need to keep their energy level high. It can be difficult for preschoolers to meet all their nutrient needs by eating just the three basic meals which are reason why snacks are important for preschooler's diet (American Academy of pediatrics, 2012). Snack foods are generally preferred by children and teenagers. In those stage of life the amount and nutritional quality of protein are important because of their essential functions in physical and mental development. Cakes are always readily available and loved by children. The addition of *moringa* to cakes will be a vehicle of essential nutrients into that diet of children and teenagers that are the major consumers of cakes.

food fortification as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO), is the practice of deliberately increasing the content of an essential micronutrient, i.e. vitamins and minerals (including trace elements) in a food irrespective of whether the nutrients were originally in the food before processing or not, so as to improve the nutritional quality of food supply and to provide a public health benefit with minimal risk to health (WHO and FAO, 2016). Staple foods of a region can lack particular nutrients due to the soil of the region or from inherent inadequacy of a normal diet. Addition of micronutrients to staples and condiments can prevent large scale deficiency disease in these cases (Copenhagen Consensus, 2017). Food fortification was identified as the second strategy of flour by the WHO and FAO to begin decreasing the incidence of nutrient deficiencies at the global level (WHO and FAO, 2016).

The most common fortified foods are cereals and cereal based products, fats and oils, accessory food items, teas and other beverages, and infants' formulas (FAO, 2016). Under nutrition and nutrient deficiency is estimated globally to cause between 3 and 5 million death per year.

The four main methods of food fortification are:

- 1) Commercial and Industrial fortification (i.e. flour, rice, oils (common cooking foods)).
- 2) Biofortification (i.e. breed crops to increase their nutritional value, which can include both conventional selective breeding, and modern genetic modification).
- 3) Synthetic biology (i.e. addition of probiotic bacteria to foods).
- 4) Home fortification (e.g. vitamin D drops) (Liyanage, C. and Hettiarachchi, M., 2011).

The WHO and FAO, among many other nationally recognized organizations, have recognized that there are over 2 billion people world wide who suffer from a variety of micronutrient deficiencies. In 1992, 159 countries pledges at the FAO/WHO International conference on nutrition to make effort to help combat these issues of micronutrient deficiencies, highlighting the importance of decreasing the number of those with iodine, vitamin A, and iron deficiencies (WHO and FAO, 2016).

Snacks fortification involves the addition of essential nutrients such as vitamins and minerals to flour foods to improve their nutritional values. In most cases, fortification can lead to rapid improvements in the micronutrients status of a population at a reasonable cost. The fortificant also should be readily available, accessible and well absorbed into the food without causing a significant change in the sensory attributes of the fortified food (Allen, *et al.*, 2006). The use of *M. oleifera* and rough lemon peels to improve the nutritional value.

Statement of Problem

Cakes and buns are major snacks in the fast food industry and highlight of many celebrations. They are highly cherished by women and children, but the major nutrient in cakes and buns do not contain much of micronutrient which are still needed for body function. This work tend to ascertain if there is a way in which this products could be fortified with more micro nutrient to add more nutrient to cake and buns to make it more rich for consumption, since foods are meant to be adequate.

Most adults avoid eating cake and buns because it contain more of carbohydrate and fat, they what to avoid weight gain, high cholesterol level in the body. Addition of rough lemon peels and *moringa* flour blends could help decrease the cholesterol level in the body and also promote weight loss. This work tend to fortify cake and

buns with *moringa* leaf and rough lemon to see if it could encourage adult to eat cake and buns with out gaining much weight and other illness.

Objective of The Study

The general objectives of the study was to examine the chemical composition and organoleptic attributes of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends and specifically to:

1. Produce cake, and buns fortified with *moringa* and rough lemon peels flour blends.
2. Determine the organoleptic attributes of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends.
3. Ascertain the chemical composition of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends.
4. Ascertain the acceptability of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peel flour blends.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. Could cake and bun be fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon feels flour blend be acceptable?
2. What is the organoleptic attributes of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends?
3. What is the chemical composition of cakes and buns fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends?
4. Could the product be acceptable?

Significance of The Study

The findings of this study was of great importance to toddlers and preschoolers, nursing mothers, nutritionist, home scientists, The beneficiaries will be the toddlers and preschoolers, it highs energy level, the amount and findings of this study was of great importance to toddlers and preschoolers, nursing mothers, nutritionist, home These scientists, the community at large, food producers and consumers and people suffering from cancer and over weight .nutritional quality of protein are important because of their essential function in physical and mental development. This study will enlighten the nursing mothers to increase the volume of breast milk produced by lactating mothers and also noted for its anti-bacterial action.

This study on the other hand will be of benefit to be Nutritionist/Home Economist in planning and preparing meals for different groups of people in the family because they have the knowledge of nutrients of *moringa oleifera* and rough lemon peels flour blend. The community will benefit from this study by knowing the importance of *moringa oleifera* and lemon peel flour blends and encourage its dwellers in the consumption of cake and buns produced from wheat, *moringa oleifera* and rough lemon peel of flour blend.

Beneficiaries will also include the food producers and consumers in that when they have the knowledge on the qualities of products from *moringa oleifera* and rough lemon peel flour blend and on its nutritional values. The findings derived from it will study can aid in nutritional education on the diversified use of *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peel. The people suffering from cancer and over weight will benefit from this study by knowing the importance of rough lemon peel and encourage its dwellers in the consumption of it. The importance of cake and buns produced from blends of wheat *moringa* leaf, and rough lemon peels flour blend, increase the nutritional status of consumer

Materials and Methods

The procedure for carrying out this study was discussed under the following sub-headings: design of the study, area of the study, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, instrument for data collection, data collection techniques, data analysis techniques, sample formulation, source of materials and determination of minerals.

Design of the Study

Experimental research design was used for this study.

Area of the Study

Home Sciences/ Hospitality Management and Tourism laboratory in College of Applied Food Sciences and Tourism (CAFST), Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, in Ikwuano Local Government Area of Abia State.

Population Of The Study

The population for the study was fifteen (15) Home Economics Lecturers and 43 final year students of Home Economics department, total population 58 (Home Economics Register, 2017).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Twenty (20) panelists formed the sample size of the study. Which were chosen through simple random sampling technique.

Instrument For Data Collection

Nine point hedonic scale questionnaire was used to determine the organoleptic properties of the samples.

Data Collection Techniques

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire (Nine point hedonic scale) which was administered to the twenty (20) trained and semi-trained panelists with the help of research assistance and the questionnaire were filled and collected immediately.

Data Analysis Techniques

Obtained data was subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Data was subjected to analysis of variance using the statistical package for social test science (SPSS), version 16.0. Results are presented as mean \pm standard deviations. One way analysis of

variance (ANOVA) was used for comparison of the means. Differences between means were considered to be significant of $P < 0.05$ using the Duncan multiple range

Sample Formulation

Four samples of cakes were produced for sensory evaluation, four samples of buns were also produced for sensory evaluation. The first sample coded W(0) was 100% wheat flour cake (the control sample). The second sample coded X was 98% wheat flour, 1% *moringa oleifera* leaf flour and 1% of rough lemon peels flour cakes. The third sample coded Y was 96% wheat flour, and 2% *moringa oleifera* leaf flour and 2% rough lemon peels flour cake. Fourth sample coded Z was 94% wheat flour, 3% *moringa oleifera* leaf flour and 3% rough lemon peels flour cake.

The sample coded A (0) was 100% of wheat flour buns. The second sample coded B was 98% wheat flour, 1% *moringa oleifera* leaf blend and 1% rough lemon peels flour buns. The third second sample coded C was 96% wheat flour, 2% *moringa oleifera* leaf flour, 2% rough lemon peels flour buns, sample D was 124% of wheat flour, 3% of *moringa oleifera* leave flour, 3% of rough lemon flour.

Water was produced for panelists to rinse their mouth between evaluations so as to draw conclusion accurately.

○ Sample formulation table

○ Samples (Cake)	○ Wheat flour	○ <i>Moringa leaf flour</i>	○ Rough lemon peels
○ Sample W(0)	○ 100%	○ 0%	○ 0%
○ Sample X	○ 98%	○ 1%	○ 1%
○ Sample Y	○ 96%	○ 2%	○ 2%
○ Sample Z	○ 94%	○ 3%	○ 3%
○ Samples (Buns)	○ Wheat flour	○ <i>Moringa leaf flour</i>	○ Rough lemon peels
○ Sample A(0)	○ 100%	○ 0%	○ 0%
○ Sample B	○ 98%	○ 1%	○ 1%
○ Sample C	○ 96%	○ 2%	○ 2%
○ Sample D	○ 94%	○ 3%	○ 3%

○ Source of Materials

- The ingredient used for the baking of the cake were wheat flour (Golden penny), sugar, butter (simas), eggs, baking powder (Bright active) which was all purchased from a local market in Umuahia, Abia state. The *moringa oleifera* powder was obtained from freshly harvested *moringa* leaves, dried at room temperature and ground to a smooth consistency and rough lemon peels powder was obtained from freshly harvested whole lemon, sun dried and ground to get the flour

DETERMINATION OF MINERALS

Determination of iron

Iron was determined following the phenanthroline method to Lee and Stumm (1960). Five milliliters of digested sample was placed in a 50ml volumetric flask. Then 3ml of phenanthroline solution, 2ml of hydrochloric acid and 1ml of hydroxylamine solution will be added to the sample in sequence. The sample solution will be boiled for 2 minutes and 9ml of ammonium acetate buffer solution was added to the solution. The solution was diluted with water to 50ml volume. The absorbance was determined at 510nm wavelength.

Iron standard solution was prepared in order to plot calibration curve to determine the prepared from 1g pure iron wires. The wires were dissolved in 100ml concentrated nitric acid, boiled in a water bath and diluted to 100ml with distilled water after cooling. Standard solution of known concentration was prepared by pipetting 2, 4, 16, 8 and 10ml standard iron solution into 100ml volumetric flask, and made up to volume.

Determination of calcium

Calcium was determined using the method described by Pearson (1976) twenty five milliliters of the digested sample will be pipetted into 250ml conical flask and a pinch of ferrochrome Black-T-Indicator (EBT) was added. Thereafter, ml of 0.1N NaOH solution will be added. Thereafter, ml of 0.1N NaOH solution will be added and the mixture will be titrated with standard EDTA (0.0ml EDTA) solution.

$$\text{Ca (mg/l)} = \frac{\text{used sample of volume}}{1000} \times \text{EMT} \times 1000$$

Where

T = titer value

M = molarities of EDTA

E = Equivalent weight of calcium

Determination of phosphorus

Phosphorus in the sample was determined according to Onwuka (2005) by molybdate method using hydroquinone as a reducing agent. Five milliliters (5ml) of the test solution will be pipetted into 50ml graduated flask. Then 10ml of molybdate mixture will be added and diluted to mark with water. It was allowed to stand for 30 minutes for colour development. The absorbance was measured at 660nm against a blank. A curve relating absorbance to mg phosphorus present will be constructed, using the phosphorus standard curve was plotted to determine the concentration of phosphorus in the sample. 100 volume of solution reading graph.

Determination of magnesium

A modification of the method of Patton and Reader (II), in which magnesium are titrated with ethylenedinitrilo tetraacetate (EDTA) using Erichrome Black T indication, was used. To prevent interference by the large amount of phosphorus present, magnesium was precipitated as magnesium ammonium phosphate from the filtrate of the calcium oxalate precipitation. This was filtered off and dissolved in 0.5N hydrochloric acid, and the analysis was continued as directed.

Determination of the mineral elements by dry ashing method

- Accurately weigh homogenous sample in duplicate 2-4gram in a crucible.
- Char the samples on a hot plate until smoking ceases

- Place charred samples in a furnace and incinerate at 525⁰C for 3-4 hrs.
- Turn off the furnace and allow the temperature to drop to 250⁰C then remove the crucible with a long thongs.
- Add 5ml 1N HNO₃ (to ensure complete removal of the ash and filter using whatman filter paper.
- Dilute or make up to mark with 1N HNO₃ and use for the analysis of the elements.
- Using the digest calcium and magnesium was determined by titrimetric method.
- Phosphorus was determined using uv-vis spectrophotometer after preparing phosphorus standards from 2ppm – 10ppm and concentration derived from standard curve.
- Sodium was determined using flame photometer after the preparation of their standards and the concentration of the elements determined form standard curve.
- Iron (Fe) was determined using AAS (atomic absorption spectrophotometer)
- **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

Table 1 Chemical Composition of cake and buns samples

Samples	Ca	Mg	P	Na	Fe
W	108.00 ^d ±1.41	20.55 ^a ±0.07	13.10 ^d ±0.14	48.75 ^d ±0.63	5.21 ^d ±0.01
X	128.00 ^c ±1.41	38.80 ^c ±0.14	15.10 ^a ±0.14	58.25 ^c ±0.07	7.11 ^c ±0.01
Y	155.50 ^b ±0.07	42.95 ^b ±0.07	16.95 ^b ±0.07	69.70 ^b ±0.14	7.51 ^b ±0.01
Z	160.50 ^a ±0.71	64.35 ^b ±0.21	20.05 ^a ±0.07	82.45 ^a ±0.07	10.40 ^b ±0.14
A	118.00 ^d ±1.41	33.85 ^d ±0.35	53.90 ^d ±0.14	3.75 ^d ±0.04	10.25 ^d ±0.07
B	265.00 ^c ±1.41	47.15 ^c ±1.20	120.85 ^c ±0.78	4.31 ^c ±0.01	13.10 ^c ±0.41
C	274.00 ^b ±1.41	52.05 ^b ±0.49	132.75 ^b ±0.07	4.51 ^b ±0.01	15.50 ^b ±0.14
D	290.00 ^a ±1.41	71.00 ^a ±0.56	145.90 ^a ±0.14	4.97 ^a ±0.01	18.85 ^a ±0.91

Table 1 above showed that the values from mean ± standard deviation of two replication ABCD means with the same superscripts in the same column are not significantly different. ABCD means with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different.

- W - 100% wheat flour cake (pure wheat cake)
- X - 98% wheat, 1% of *moringa* leaf, 1% of rough lemon peels
- Y - 96% wheat, 2% of *moringa* leaf and 2% of rough lemon peels.
- Z - 94% wheat 2% of *moringa* leaf and 3% of rough lemon peels.
- A - 100% wheat flour cake

- B - 98% wheat, 1% of *moringa* leaf and 1% of rough lemon peels
- C - 96% wheat, 2% of *moringa* leaf and 2% of rough lemon peels
- D - 94% wheat, 3% of *moringa* leaf and 3% of rough lemon peels.

Table.2 Organoleptic Properties of Cake Sample

Samples	Taste	Appearance/ Colour	Flavour	Texture	General acceptability
W	8.10 ^a ±0.99	7.60 ^a ±0.57	7.90 ^a ±0.57	7.90 ^a ±0.99	8.00 ^a ±0.82
X	8.10 ^a ±0.99	8.50 ^a ±0.53	8.10 ^a ±0.74	8.20 ^a ±0.63	8.50 ^{ab} ±0.53
Y	7.40 ^a ±0.97	6.40 ^b ±0.96	7.00 ^a ±1.41	7.70 ^a ±1.06	7.30 ^b ±0.82
Z	7.50 ^a ±1.43	6.60 ^b ±1.58	7.10 ^a ±1.52	7.40 ^a ±1.89	7.50 ^b ±1.18

Results of sensory evaluation of the produced cake with inclusion of *moringa* leaf and rough lemon peels are shown in the tastes. The result show that most variations in the scores of the sensory attributes were not of significant difference. Sample W (control sample) and X (Sample C containing 98% wheat, 1% *moringa* leaf and rough lemon peel flour) had the highest value 8.10^a±0.99. While Sample Y had the lowest value. From hedonic scale, 8 translate to like very much while 7 translate to like moderately therefore, sample W & X was like very much intake by the panelist.

Table .3 Organoleptic properties of buns samples

Samples	Taste	Appearance/ Colour	Flavour	Texture	General acceptability
A	8.00 ^a ±1.49	8.20 ^a ±0.32	7.90 ^a ±1.52	7.70 ^a ±1.57	7.90 ^a ±1.29
B	7.50 ^{ab} ±1.17	6.30 ^a ±1.06	6.90 ^a ±1.59	6.90 ^a ±1.45	7.00 ^{ab} ±1.25
C	6.10 ^b ±2.02	5.90 ^b ±2.18	6.60 ^a ±1.84	6.50 ^a ±1.78	5.90 ^b ±1.52
D	6.60 ^{ab} ±1.78	5.70 ^b ±2.49	6.30 ^a ±2.36	6.60 ^a ±1.96	5.90 ^b ±2.18

The results of the sensory evaluation of the produced buns with inclusion of *moringa* leaf, rough lemon peels and what are shown in colour, taste, colour, texture. The result show that most variations in the scores of the sensory attributes are of significant difference.

Discussion

Table 1 showed the chemical composition revealed that the calcium content of *moringa* powder is more than two times than that of milk, and its iron content is more than that of spinach (Gopalakrishnan *et al.*, 2016). The calcium value of 124g wheat, 3g of rough lemon peels and *moringa* leaf reported in this study is highest value of 160.50±0.71 and the control sample which contain 130g of wheat cake had the least value of 108.00±1.41.

Phosphorus are important component of cell and body fluids that help control heart beat rate and blood pressure. The 94% of wheat, 3% of *moringa* and 3% of rough lemon peels had highest value of 20.05±0.07 while 100% wheat cake had the least value of 13.10±0.14. There was significantly difference (P<0.05).

The 124g of wheat and 3g of *moringa* leaf and rough lemon peels had the highest value of 64.35 ± 0.21 of magnesium and $10.400.4$ of iron while 100% wheat (control sample had the least value 20.55 ± 0.07 of magnesium and 5.21 ± 0.01 of iron. The score for colour of cakes ranges between $6.40^b \pm 0.96$ (sample Y containing 96% wheat, 2% *moringa* leaf and 2% rough lemon peels flour) to $8.50^a \pm 0.53$ (sample X containing 98% wheat, 1% *moringa* leaf and 1% rough lemon flour). The sample X containing 98% wheat, 1% *moringa* and rough lemon peels cake scored higher $8.50^a \pm 0.53$ than the other produced composite flour cakes and whole wheat flour cake. The variation in colour score of the sample were of significant difference ($P < 0.05$) colour in an essential sensory attributes which determines the aesthetic value of foods.

The flavor recorded high score for the cakes $8.10^a \pm 0.74$. While the lowest score value $7.00^a \pm 1.41$. There is no significant different among the samples ($P > 0.05$). The score for texture of cakes range between $7.40^a \pm 1.89$ (Sample Z containing 94% wheat, 3% *moringa* leaf and 3% rough lemon peels flour) to $8.20^a \pm 0.63$ (Sample X containing 98% wheat, 1% *moringa* leaf and rough lemon peels flour) which had the higher score.

The 98% wheat, 1% *moringa* leaf and 1% rough lemon peels flour had the most accepted with a score $8.50^a \pm 0.53$, from hedonic scale, 8 translate to like very much; therefore sample X was like very much by the panelist. The scores of taste ranged between $6.10^b \pm 2.02$ (Sample C containing 95% wheat, 2% *moringa* leaf and 2% rough lemon peels flour) to $8.00^a \pm 1.49$ (control sample). The whole wheat flour bun scored higher $8.00^a \pm 1.49$ than the composite flour buns. The variation of the produce samples was of significant different ($P > 0.05$). The mean scores for the colour of the buns showed significant difference, the control sample had highest scores $8.20^a \pm 0.32$ while the composite sample scored $6.30^a \pm 1.10$, $5.90^b \pm 2.18$ and $5.70^b \pm 2.49$.

The flavor recorded high scores for the buns sample $6.90^a \pm 1.59$ to $7.90^a \pm 1.52$. The scores for the textures ranged $6.50^a \pm 1.78$ (Sample C containing 96% wheat flour, 2% *moringa* leaf and 2% rough lemon peels flour) which had the least score to $7.70^a \pm 1.57$ which had the highest score. There were no significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

The 1% *moringa* leaf, rough lemon peels and 98% wheat flour were most accepted among the composite flour. This study focused on the chemical composition and organoleptic attributes of cakes and buns produced from wheat fortified with *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels flour blends. The chemical composition, nutritional benefits and medicinal benefits were determined. The sensory evaluation of this research work was conducted using 20 semi-trained and trained panelist and the result shows that there is variation on taste, colour, flavor, texture and general acceptability level of *moringa oleifera* leaf and rough lemon peels and that of wheat flour.

Iron value of the cake products differed significantly ($P < 0.05$). The 94% wheat, 3% *moringa* leaf and 3% of rough lemon peels had the highest value of 10.40 ± 0.14 while the 100% wheat (control sample had the least value of 5.21 ± 0.01). This work was compared with Fummulayo Ajibola (2015) asserted the iron highest value 6.23 ± 0.13 and above is an indication of over baking method. Iron is an essential nutritional element. Function of iron include involvement in energy metabolism, gene regulation, cell growth and differentiation, oxygen binding and transport, muscle oxygen use and storage, enzyme reactions and protein synthesis.

Recommendation

Based on the followings, recommendations are as follows:

- 1) I recommend the use of *moringa* flour in the production of cakes and buns because of its health benefits.
- 2) Families, individual should be encouraged or taught about rough lemon peels, to avoid wastage through workshop, seminar and conference.

3) The flour obtained from *moringa oleifera* and rough lemon peels can be used as composite in baking of confectionar

4) Conclusion

The research work was able to identify the chemical composition of *moringa* and rough lemon peels in the production of cakes and buns, this will increase the nutritional status of consumers, especially children and teenagers that are the major consumers of cakes,

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